

TEACHING COMBINATION CLASSES IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Combination classes have become a common practice in many Public Elementary Schools due to many factors such as limited teaching staff, low number of pupils enrollment and classroom shortages. The purpose of this study is to described the experiences, challenges and coping strategies of teachers handling combination classes. The study utilized a qualitative research design with in-depth interview as the primary source of data. Participants were teachers teaching combination classes. The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, which involved transcription, coding, categorization, and identification of emerging themes. The findings revealed there are several key areas related to the experiences of teachers handling combination classes such as Combination Class Lesson Planning, Delivery of Instruction, Teaching Strategy, Classroom Management, Learning Resources and Assessment and Evaluation. With these experiences, teachers encounter challenges such as Evaluation Difficulties, Behavioral Challenges and Learning Resources. Despite these difficulties, teachers developed strategies that includes Adaptive Professional Growth, Preparedness and support to balance their personal well-being and the obligations. In conclusion, teaching in combination class is complex and demanding. With all its experiences, teachers are required to be flexible, resourceful and adaptive in their situation. Despite all the challenges encountered, teachers remained resilient and flexible through employing coping strategies. Through this, it helped maintained the instructional effectiveness of teachers teaching combination class and create a learning environment that is supportive to the needs of their diverse pupils.

Keywords: *Combination classes, Experiences, Challenges Coping Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Combination classes is an instructional setting wherein pupils from two grade levels are taught together within the same classroom by a single teacher. Unlike a traditional single-grade class or monograde classroom, combination classes facilitates learners from different ages, comprehension level and developmental ages into one learning environment. Combination class is a significant and suitable method to assist countries in fulfilling the globally mandated Education for All objectives and the National Millennium Development Goals by offering high-quality learners who are frequently overlooked by the education system as a result of their isolated, depopulated, and tiny communities (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2015).

In the Philippines, Elementary Education is the foundation a child's development socially and academically. Elementary Schools are tasked with delivering education that is aligned with the national curriculum as mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd).

Combination classes provide a special educational opportunity where learners of all ages study together, encouraging cooperation and a sense of community (Mathot, 2001). Combination classes have different needs from monograde classes, including more teacher preparation, classroom materials, and thorough teacher evaluation. Teachers feel that there is too much work in combination classrooms from preparing lesson plans, classroom management techniques, educational facilities, instructional materials, and community support that contribute and improve learning outcomes. (Napanan, 2021).

In combination classes, the lesson plan serves as a road map of teacher perceptions and practices, providing insight into their preferences regarding instruction and curriculum (Alrwaished, 2024). Teachers should have relevant expertise, creativity and innovative pedagogies, and practical teaching abilities in teaching combination classes (Şanlı et al., 2016). There are various teaching strategies and learning styles utilized in combination classes and these methods mostly focuses according to pupils' learning capacities. Educational principles and pedagogy focus on the type of pupils' learning and the classroom environment (Abulhul, 2021). The teaching and learning process must center to pupils to deliver excellent educational services (Demchenko et.al., 2021). Additionally, classroom management should compose a set of strategies that is important for maintaining a well-organized learning environment. These strategies form a comprehensive approach to effective classroom management in a combination class setting. The implementation of such strategies is pivotal, as highlighted by Chalak and Fallah (2019). Moreover, Learning resource such as textbooks, visual aids and as well as digital tools like online learning platforms, educational software, and interactive media are utilized in combination classes. Assessments are localized and teacher-centered, and involve oral examinations or written tests tailored to specific classrooms and curricula (Vinovskis, 2019).

Teaching combination classes has advantages, studies reveal that teachers perceive teaching these classes is more stressful than teaching monograde classes. Mulryan-Kyne (2004) noted that, teachers may prefer teaching monograde class if given a choice for the reason that monograde class has a straightforward curriculum and classroom management. In combination classes, it is a challenge in making assessments as it should be constructed and adjusted to be flexible to the needs of the learners. It is important to keep pupils engaged in their learning by giving them assignments that is beyond the classroom curriculum and is related to the experiences of the pupils (Agtarap, 2024). Cornish (2012) argued that it is more challenging to teach combination classes compared to single-grade classes with pupils at the same level. Larger class sizes pose additional challenges for teachers, such as setting and enforcing behavioral expectations, monitoring pupils and providing individual attention. Teachers highlighted the challenge of managing a class with varied behaviors given the different levels of pupils. Moreover, limited access to learning resources, that includes books and technology, affects the effectiveness of teaching and learning, making it difficult for teachers to implement engaging and comprehensive lessons (Bernales & Constantino, 2024).

Being faced with different challenges, combination classes teachers apply coping strategies to deal with their situations. According to Good (1959), adjustment means finding and adopting behaviors that align with their environment or situation or adapting to changes within it (as cited in Mangal, 2016). This means that a teachers can either conform to their surroundings or modify their environment to suit their needs. Wilson (2003) emphasized that combination classes require more time and organization, and teachers with specialized training in instructing mixed-age groups.

Moreover, combination classes are widely used in schools with limited resources wherein teachers handle pupils from different grade levels in one classroom. While existing literature highlights challenges faced by combination class teachers . There is a significant gap in the study of combination classes. Specifically, there is limited data on how combination classes are employed in terms of actual teaching.

Research Questions

Generally, the study described teaching combination classes in Public Elementary Schools based on the experiences of teachers.

Specifically, the study answered the following:

1. What are the experiences of teachers in teaching combination classes?
2. What are the challenges encountered in teaching combination classes?
3. What are the coping strategies employed in addressing the challenges?
4. What framework in teaching combination classes be designed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was a descriptive qualitative study which aimed to describe experiences of teachers handling combination classes in Public Elementary Schools. This study focused on capturing the participant's perspectives and presenting the data in rich, descriptive narratives.

Descriptive qualitative design was utilized as it is appropriate for this study because it seeks to provide a straightforward and detailed information of the participant's experiences, challenges and coping strategies in teaching combination classes. Descriptive qualitative was also the most suitable for this study because it provides in-depth insights into real classroom scenarios and allows the voices of participants to be clearly presented.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Schools Division of South Cotabato. The Division is located at the Province of South Cotabato, Region XII. Specifically, the study was limited to schools with combination classes.

School A is located in Sitio Lambalas, Brgy. Rang-ay, Banga South Cotabato and an extension school of Rang-ay Integrated School having fifty-two pupils from Kindergarten to Grade-six, the school offers three combination classes.

School B is located in Sitio Demlong, Brgy Halilan, Lake Sebu, South Cotabato. An extension school of Haliland Integrated School with with fifty-five pupils. The school also offers three combination classes.

School C is located in Sitio Akbang, Brgy. Tablu, Tampakan, South Cotabato with sixty-one pupils and an extension school of Tablu Elementary School. It has three combination classes.

School D is located in Sitio Kafok, Acmonan, Tupi, South Cotabato with forty-four pupils and extension school of Acmonan Integrated School that also offers three combination classes.

School E is located in Sitio Lam-lago, Brgy. Datal Bob, T'boli, South Cotabato with seventeen pupils and extension school of Datal Bob Elementary School and offers two combination classes.

Sources of Data

Participants. The Participants of the study was the teachers from the Schools Division of South Cotabato. Specifically, teachers on five chosen municipalities who are teaching combination classes.

Documents. Documents such lesson plans and lesson exemplar were also part of the source of data because they serve as a documentary evidence and it provide structured and intentional evidence of the teaching practices of the teachers as well as their instructional design and curriculum implementation in teaching combination classes. These documents helped strengthened the credibility of the findings.

Observation Data. Observation data was utilized in the study by directly watching and systematically recording the behaviors that occur during the observation. The observation captured what really happened in the classroom and it makes it a powerful source of evidence in the study.

Research Instrument

This study aimed to describe the experiences of teachers teaching combination classes in Public Elementary School. An in-depth interview was done in the study and an in-depth interview guide was utilized to gather the data. The statement of the problem was the guide of the researcher to get and capture interesting concepts and follow-up questions were also used to explore the phenomenon. Document Review Checklist was also utilized to systematically collect and analyze data from materials that are relevant to the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following were the procedures in gathering data for this study. The researcher seek approval from the Graduate School Dean. Once approved, the researcher undergone the Ethics Review Board. In this, the researcher complied all the necessary requirements. The researcher also requested a Certification from the National Commission of Indigenous Peoples as an additional requirement to the Ethics Review Board. After thorough checking and release of the certificate to conduct from the Ethical Review Board, the researcher secured a permit from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. A dry run of the interview was done to improve the conduct of the interview. After the dry run, it was subjected to checking of the Adviser and once approved, the researcher seek permission from the school heads of the chosen schools to let the researcher conduct the study. An in-depth interview guide was used as a primary instrument for data collection. Probing questions was also included in order to elicit more elaboration and deeper reflection from the participants for necessity. The interview was recorded using a mobile phone and the researcher also informed the participants about taking picture during the observation. The researcher also informed the participants about the ethical considerations of the research as well as informed them that the study has undergone ethical review to ensure that the rights and the well-being of the participants

is protected. During the observation of all participants, the researcher sits in the class of the participant while the participant is teaching to observe whether the teacher displayed practices that was mentioned during the interview. Taking of photos were also done as a visual evidence that supports the observation process.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized thematic analysis in analyzing and interpreting the gathered data. This approach was utilized to enable researcher to describe the experiences, challenges and coping strategies of teachers handling combination classes and enable researcher to organize these experiences into meaningful themes. Responses of the participants were transcribed, coded, categorized and developed into themes. Moreover, to strengthen the validity of the findings, the researcher incorporate direct quotations from the answers of the participants to support each identified themes. These quotations becomes and evidence that the themes identified were grounded on the actual responses of the participants.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on describing the teaching of combination classes in Public Elementary School which aims to describe the experiences of the teachers in combination classes, the challenges encountered and the coping strategies employed by the teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiences in Teaching Combination Classes

Actual teaching provide a meaningful experience in a classroom setting. It allows teachers to face pupils with different personalities, learning styles and abilities that can be challenging but rewarding at the same time.

Combination Classes Lesson Planning

In combination class lesson planning, two categories emerged as themes namely: Combination Class Lesson Planning Approaches and Curriculum-Guided as basis for Lesson Planning.

Combination Class Lesson Planning Approaches. The findings indicate that lesson planning in combination classrooms requires a flexible, adaptive approach given differences in grade-level content and learner abilities. Multiple lesson plan formats helps teachers meet the different needs of learners at different levels by separating lesson plan for each grade level and utilizing one lesson plan with the same topic. the lesson plan serves as a road map of teacher perceptions and practices, providing insight into their preferences regarding instruction and curriculum (Alrwaished, 2024).

Curriculum-Guide as Basis for Lesson Planning. The findings indicate that participants rely heavily on the Department of Education's curriculum guides and provision of curriculum guide is the basis for preparing lessons. This is consistent with Bunga et al. (2025), who state that combination teaching underscores the importance of aligning lessons with the curriculum and using structured planning tools.

Delivery of Instruction

In delivery of instruction, three categories emerged as themes, namely: Simultaneous Combination Class Engagement, Differentiated Instructional Strategies, and Tailored-Appropriate Teaching Strategies.

Simultaneous Combination Class Engagement. Findings on this themes shows that teachers in combination classrooms often teach two grade levels in the same room. In order to deliver lesson, teachers separates each class. According to Bonghala et al. (2020), a teacher might introduce new material to one group while the other works on assigned tasks, then switch roles when the first group is done. A teacher may start with a pre-assessment for one grade while teaching another, then alternate between teaching, guiding activities, and assessments for each group.

Differentiated Instructional Strategies. The findings show that pupils in combination classrooms benefit from using visual aids and daily practice. Pupils has different interests. Thus, teachers find way to make class interesting. This aligns with research indicating that teachers should vary instructional materials and activities to meet the diverse needs of children across different grades and ages (Quail & Smyth, 2014).

Tailored-Appropriate Teaching Strategies. The findings of this study reveal that teachers in combination classrooms implement teaching strategies carefully tailored to learners' grade levels and abilities. Like, teachers give examples that are appropriate for the pupil's grade level. Lower grade level pupils engaged in visual and simple tasks that are guided by the teacher, while the higher grade level pupils are in more complex tasks that involve reading, understanding, and speaking. So therefore, tasks in a combination classes are adjusted so everyone works with content that fits their level (Bumacas & Asuncion, 2025).

Teaching Strategy

In Teaching strategy there is one category that emerged as theme namely: Peer Tutoring Instructional Approach.

Peer Tutoring Instructional Approach. The results indicate that participants utilize learner-centered practices to effectively manage a combination classroom and address the diverse learning needs of pupils. The buddy-buddy method, also known as peer tutoring, is a key component of this strategy. Teacher uses the buddy system so that higher grade pupils can help lower grade pupils. This is can be highlighted to the study that peer tutoring is a practical educational approach that benefits both tutors and tutees by enhancing understanding, promoting active learning, and building a supportive classroom environment (Atamosa & Dioso, 2024).

Contextualization

In contextualization, two categories emerged as themes, namely: Locally Relevant Teaching Strategies, Relatable and Experiential Teaching.

Locally Relevant Teaching Strategies. This theme shows that combination class teachers, just like formal classroom teachers, also employ contextualized and localized instruction by integrating examples from the pupils' daily lives and immediate surroundings. According to Alviar-Martin & Baildon (2019) to make courses meaningful, localized and contextualized instruction, frequently employed in combination classrooms and rural classrooms, uses genuine objects (realia) community examples, and pupils' real-life experiences.

Relatable and Experiential Teaching. The theme reveals that the teacher employs community-connected and contextualized instruction to enhance pupils' understanding and engagement. Thus, teacher teaches learners according to their experiences and interests. According to Mahabadi (2012), the idea of localization assumes that pupils learn more effectively when their classroom experiences are meaningful and significant to them.

Classroom Management

In Classroom Management, two categories emerged as themes namely: Organized and Structured Combination Class Teaching, Behavior and Routine Management.

Organized and Structured Combination Class Teaching. Effective classroom management and routines are crucial in a combination class setting. The findings reveal that the teacher employs combination class classroom management strategies to address the challenges of teaching two grade levels in a single classroom. Teachers disciplines learners individually. This strategy ensures the desired learning is achieved and continues smoothly for both groups, maintaining order and active participation throughout the lesson. Teachers create structured environments through consistent activities, improving classroom dynamics (Bagay, 2024).

Class Teaching, Behavior and Routine Management. This theme shows that combination class teachers emphasize the utilization of classroom behavior management style to maintain order, focus, and positive behavior among learners. When pupils becomes unruly, teacher utilizes reward system. Such strategies are rooted in behaviorist theory, as a means of shaping desirable behavior (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015).

Learning Resources

In Learning Resources, two categories emerged as themes namely: Instructional Technology Utilization and Printed and Digital Learning Materials.

Instructional Technology Utilization. The availability of ICT tools has generally improved teaching practices. Teachers in combination classroom multimedia tools such

as gadgets and TV to deliver lessons. This theme resonates with Taole and Mncube (2012), who emphasized the value of integrating technology to improve instructional delivery, particularly in under-resourced and remote contexts.

Printed and Digital Learning Materials. The results show that the teacher uses a range of teaching resources and visual aids to improve pupils' learning. Teachers prepares visuals for printing and uses traditional teaching methods. The availability of such resources supports differentiated learning, ensuring that all pupils, regardless of ability or pace, have access to structured learning materials. Teachers must select, create, and adapt didactic materials to meet their classrooms' needs for effective combination teaching (Naparan & Alinsug, 2021; Smit et al., 2015).

Assessment and Evaluation

In assessment and evaluation, one category emerged as themes namely: Contextualized Differentiated Assessment.

Contextualized Differentiated Assessment. The findings indicate that combination class teachers implement contextualized and differentiated assessment practices to monitor pupils' learning effectively. Teacher gives weekly assessments. This aligns with research showing that differentiated assessment promotes equity, equality, and inclusivity in highly diverse classroom settings (Tomlinson, 2017).

Challenges in Teaching Combination Class

Teaching combination class with different grade levels that has distinct abilities, learning goals and academic levels can be demanding. Teachers must carefully balance teaching in a combination class to ensure that all pupils receive appropriate attention without neglecting other pupils.

Evaluation Difficulties

In Evaluation Difficulties, there is one category that emerged as theme namely: Designing and Implementing Challenges in Evaluation

Designing and Implementing Challenges in Evaluation. The findings showed that teachers face considerable challenges when creating and applying evaluations. Teacher finds it difficult to give clear instructions in varied assessments. Valdez & Escueta (2021) emphasize that a key challenge in combination class is designing assessments that align with each grade's curriculum and match pupils' developmental stages.

Behavioral Challenges

In Behavioral Challenges, there is one category that emerged as theme namely: Complexities of Combination Classroom Management

Complexities of Combination Classroom Management. The findings reveal that it is a struggle balancing instruction and classroom discipline as the teacher struggles to manage the class when pupils have different levels of lesson progress and comprehension. It is emphasized that managing a combination class is one of the most challenging experiences for a teacher. When pupils are at different grade levels, some finish lessons quickly while others are still struggling, creating confusion and requiring constant multitasking (Gage et al., 2018).

Learning Resources

In Learning Resources there is one category that emerged as theme namely: Inadequate Resources

Inadequate Resources. The findings reveal that teachers experience considerable challenges due to the lack of instructional resources in their respective schools. Teachers consistently expressed that the absence of sufficient teaching materials wherein teachers struggle in not having enough resources. Teachers will need to deliberate and reflect on the teaching materials they have, or create new ones, that align with the active-participatory and globalized teaching strategies used and the intended classroom objectives (Abos et al., 2021; García et al., 2017).

Coping Strategy in Teaching Combination Classes

Teaching combination class requires flexibility and creativity. Everyday experience presents unique challenges to teachers. Despite all the challenges the teacher learns to celebrate small wins to gradually develop resilience and to escape exhaustion and pressure.

Adaptive Professional Growth

In Adaptive Professional Growth, there is one category that emerged as theme namely: Experienced-Driven Adaptation

Experienced-Driven Adaptation. Teachers in combination class show that although the task is challenging, it becomes manageable over time, with experience and commitment. Teachers emphasize the relevance of experience in teaching combination class and becoming used to the set-up. Despite being placed in resource-constrained, remote environments and often without formal preparation for combination instruction, they continuously rise to the occasion, adapting, innovating, and growing. Their narratives reflect how challenges became catalysts for transformation, shaping both their personal and professional identities (Jimenez, 2025).

Preparedness

In Preparedness there are two categories that emerged as theme namely: Instructional Preparedness and Strategic Time Management.

Instructional Preparedness. Proper preparation helps teachers plan their lessons clearly, making the teaching process smoother, more comprehensible, and reducing stress for both teachers and pupils. Teachers emphasize preparedness in delivering instruction. According to Santos (2011), to ensure learners' learning, the combination class teacher needs to apply multiple strategies to reduce the waiting time between pupils' activities.

Strategic Time Management. Strategic time management emerged as an essential theme in teachers' experiences, particularly in addressing the demands of combination classrooms. Since teachers utilize strategic time allocation in teaching combination class. Jimenez (2025) stated, combination teachers optimize limited instructional time through planning and adaptability, enabling them to meet diverse student needs without compromising learning outcomes.

Support System

In Support System there is one category that emerged as theme, namely: Professional Support.

Professional Support. The findings reveal that teachers rely heavily on a strong network of professional and emotional support systems to manage their instructional responsibilities, particularly when handling combination classes, slow learners, and non-readers. Senior teachers, co-teachers, and school heads play a vital role in guiding and motivating teachers through shared inputs. According to Sampson and Condy (2016), Peer-Learning communities are essential for raising teacher confidence and improving the quality of instruction.

Conclusions

With due considerations of the findings, it is concluded that teaching in combination class is complex and demanding. With all its experiences, teachers are required to be flexible, resourceful and adaptive in their situation. Teachers must be able to integrate lesson planning, instructional delivery, classroom management and assessment in a class with diverse pupils. Teaching in combination classrooms presents unique challenges that test teachers' skills, adaptability, and resilience. Evaluation, classroom management, and learning resources must be carefully considered due to the complexity of managing pupils across grade levels. In addition to adding to the workload of educators, these difficulties necessitate creative thinking, mental stability, and professional preparedness in order to guarantee successful instruction. Teaching also goes beyond the given teaching strategies, requiring teachers to become innovative in terms of contextualization and providing learning resources. Despite all the challenges encountered, teachers remained resilient and flexible through employing coping strategies that helped improve the teaching of combination classes. Teacher's quality of instruction and their well-being are both supported by interrelated aspects that shaped the effective teaching of combination class teachers. Through this, it helped maintain the instructional effectiveness of teachers teaching combination class and create a learning environment that is supportive to the needs of their diverse pupils.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations:

1. Utilize the proposed framework as a guide in planning and assessing instruction in combination class.
2. Conduct training with the considerations of the proposed framework.
3. Implement program that would regularly evaluate the effectiveness of teaching combination classes.

Figure 1. Proposed Framework in Teaching Combination Classes

The figure shows the Proposed Framework in Teaching Combination Classes. This framework is from the findings of the experiences, challenges and coping mechanism of the teachers in teaching combination classes. It discussed as follows:

Lesson Planning

Need for Flexible and Adaptive Teacher Training. Teachers must be highly adaptable and flexible to meet the varied demands of students at different grade levels in combination classrooms.

Delivery of Instruction

Promoting Collaborative Learning and Peer Tutoring. This implies that it is beneficial to create a collaborative learning environment in which advanced pupils support struggling pupils.

Teaching Strategy

Focus on Resource Accessibility and Innovation. This emphasizes the need for schools to prioritize access to affordable educational technologies and resources, while also encouraging teachers to adapt existing tools to meet their students' needs creatively.

Classroom Management Through Structured Routines. Strategic planning is necessary for classroom management in combination classrooms.

Contextualization

Integration of Contextualized and Experiential Learning. This underscores the importance of providing pupils with a relatable, meaningful education.

Classroom Management

Comprehensive Support for Classroom Management. This finding underscores the need for educational programs suited to a combination class setting that prepare teachers to design structured classroom environments that facilitate smooth transitions between grade levels.

Learning Resources

Curriculum and Instructional Material Development. Educational authorities should consider revisiting curriculum guidelines to allow greater flexibility, incorporating recommendations for differentiated, modular lesson plans that can serve multiple grade levels simultaneously.

Assessment and Evaluation

Adaptation of Assessment Practices. The results emphasize the significance of adaptable, varied assessment methods that accommodate different skill and readiness levels.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that they adhere with the ethical standards all throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent forms was obtain from the participants before the data collection. Researcher ensured that the participation of the participants was voluntary. Participants are well informed that they can withdraw anytime from the study without penalty. They are also informed that their identity will remain anonymous and confidential by excluding any identification and information. All the data that was gathered was handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act in order to protect the participants' information. Participants' well-being was safeguarded. There were no psychological or social harm resulted from the conduct of the study. To avoid plagiarism, proper citation of sources and objectivity were done to prevent bias in the interpretation of the study. Lastly, the results and findings of these study was used solely for academic purposes only.

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